

**NEW REHABILITATION AGAINST ELECTRONIC
CRIMES BY YOUNG PEOPLE**Nueva rehabilitación contra delitos electrónicos
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13732745>**RESUMEN**

The rising prevalence of cybercrimes committed by young individuals has emerged as a notable concern. In 2020, the FBI recorded over 240,000 incidents involving young criminals, highlighting the urgent need for effective rehabilitation methods. The articles aim to develop and evaluate a new rehabilitation method for young cybercriminals to address the limitations of punitive actions such as fines, community service, and probation. The proposed approach integrates restorative justice, therapy, and education to address the root causes that contribute to cybercriminal activity in young persons. Preliminary findings suggest that the innovative rehabilitation method reduces the likelihood of participants engaging in further criminal activities and enhances their mental well-being. By prioritizing restorative justice, treatment, and education, there is the possibility of significantly transforming lives, reducing rates of electronic crime, and generating significant financial savings for the criminal justice system.

Palabras claves: Electronic crimes, youth offenders, rehabilitation, restorative justice.

ABSTRACT

La creciente prevalencia de delitos cibernéticos cometidos por jóvenes se ha convertido en una preocupación notable. En 2020, el FBI registró más de 240.000 incidentes que involucraron a delincuentes jóvenes, lo que pone de relieve la necesidad urgente de métodos de rehabilitación eficaces. Los artículos tienen como objetivo desarrollar y evaluar un nuevo método de rehabilitación para jóvenes ciberdelinquentes para abordar las limitaciones de las acciones punitivas, como multas, servicio comunitario y libertad condicional. El enfoque propuesto integra la justicia restaurativa, la terapia y la educación para abordar las causas fundamentales que contribuyen a la actividad ciberdelictiva en los jóvenes. Los hallazgos preliminares sugieren que el innovador método de rehabilitación reduce la probabilidad de que los participantes participen en más actividades delictivas y mejora su bienestar mental. Al priorizar la justicia restaurativa, el tratamiento y la educación, existe la posibilidad de transformar significativamente las vidas, reducir las tasas de delitos electrónicos y generar importantes ahorros financieros para el sistema de justicia penal.

Keywords: Delitos electrónicos, delincuentes juveniles, rehabilitación, justicia restaurativa.

INTRODUCTION

Younger generations increasingly commit cybercrimes, which pose a significant danger to people, businesses, and society. In 2021, the National Cyber Security Alliance conducted a survey and found that forty percent of children under eighteen had been victims of cyberbullying, while twenty-six percent had their identities stolen [1]. The currently used approaches to rehabilitation, which include the imposition of fines, the need for community service, and the placement of individuals on probation, have been criticized for their lack of efficacy and the stigma they perpetuate [2]

An innovative approach to youth rehabilitation is proposed in this article as a potential course of action for young people who have engaged in unlawful actions with technology equipment. The new technique, which is beneficial in reducing recidivism rates and improving young people's mental health, includes elements of restorative justice, counseling, and education [3]

Throughout the review of the relevant literature, we will investigate the current situation of the research field on the topic of rehabilitating young people whose criminal behavior includes using electronic devices. In addition, we will do a literature review of essential papers, bringing to light contentious and conflicting hypotheses when the context calls for it. In particular, we will talk about the issues that exist with the approaches currently being used, as well as the challenges that need to be surmounted to implement new rehabilitation programs.

As the previous sentence implied, the newly proposed rehabilitation approach for adolescents and young adults who have committed cybercrimes is not a silver bullet. A customized rehabilitation method is required

for the most spectacular outcomes in each circumstance. To accomplish this objective, there must be a collaboration between the legal system, professionals in the field of mental health, and educational institutions [4].

One of the primary benefits of the new technique that has been recommended is that it will allow the criminal justice system to save money. When juveniles commit crimes in digital technology, the expenses of investigating and prosecuting such crimes may rapidly increase. Investing in rehabilitation programs that prevent future technology crimes may result in long-term cost savings for the criminal justice system [5], [6] [7], [8].

Investigating the factors that lead young people to engage in criminal activity online is also necessary. Many young people who commit these crimes may deal with underlying issues such as poor mental health, a lack of social support, and inadequate educational or career possibilities. If these underlying issues are addressed, young people may not commit crimes in the future and will have more meaningful lives.

A possible solution to a growing problem is an innovative way of rehabilitating young people who have committed online crimes. Even if there are barriers to implementation, such as resistance to change and a lack of money, the potential benefits, such as decreased recidivism rates and improved mental health outcomes, make it a worthwhile investment. Effective rehabilitation programs must be emphasized in order to both prevent and protect victims of cybercrime.

The study objective

This article aims to provide a new strategy for rehabilitating young people who have committed offenses related to electronic media. By arguing for the employment of restorative justice, counseling, and education, the article aims to overcome the li-

mits of conventional rehabilitation techniques such as fining, community service, and probation. It also strives to address these shortcomings. This article intends to emphasize the potential advantages of this novel method, including lower recidivism rates, better mental health outcomes for juvenile offenders, and financial savings for the criminal justice system. In addition, the purpose of this article is to increase awareness of the problems that will be presented by the adoption of this new method, such as opposition to change and a lack of financing. The overarching aim of this article is to advocate for the implementation of a method that is both more efficient and all-encompassing in terms of rehabilitating young people who have been found guilty of committing offenses using electronic devices.

Problem statement

It is a developing concern that presents a substantial danger to individuals, organizations, and society because young people commit a rising number of crimes, including using technological devices. Conventional rehabilitation methods, such as paying fines, doing community service, and being placed on probation, have come under fire for their perceived ineffectiveness and ability to stigmatize offenders. The existing system has not been successful in stopping young people from committing more offenses, and it needs to address the underlying problems that may have led to their committing the act in the first place. Consequently, a new treatment method is required for young people who have committed crimes using electronic devices. The problem statement is that the current strategy to rehabilitate young people who have committed electronic crimes needs to be revised. A different method focusing on restorative justice, counseling, and education is required to prevent future offenses and promote positive outcomes for young people.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The increasing involvement of young individuals in cybercrimes has prompted the need to reevaluate existing rehabilitation methods. Despite the growing body of research on juvenile delinquency and rehabilitation, there are gaps in effectively addressing the unique challenges posed by cybercrime. This literature review compiles data from several studies to highlight the current shortcomings and provide an innovative rehabilitation approach to address youth participation in electronic crimes.

Traditional methods of rehabilitation, such as imposing financial penalties, assigning community service, and adopting probation, have been widely used but have been criticized for their limited effectiveness in lowering recidivism rates among adolescent offenders [9], [10]. These techniques often fail to address the underlying causes of delinquent conduct, such as inadequate education, limited social support, and mental health issues [11]. Furthermore, the adverse view associated with criminal histories might hinder the reintegration process into society, exacerbating the challenges faced by those with such records [2].

Emerging approaches, such as restorative justice, have shown promise in addressing some challenges. The study by Latimer, Jeff, Dowden, Craig, & Muise, Danielle [12] indicates that restorative justice techniques are more effective than traditional methods in lowering the probability of recidivism among juvenile offenders. Kettrey and Lipsey's study showed that targeted treatment regimens for juvenile sex offenders significantly decrease the likelihood of them committing further offenses. However, these strategies have not been specifically tailored to address cybercrimes, which present unique challenges and need specialist interventions [13].

A notable gap in the current literature is the lack of research on rehabilitation initiatives specifically designed for young individuals involved in electronic crimes. While research has been conducted on several areas of adolescent delinquency and rehabilitation [10], [14], there is a dearth of evidence about treatments that mainly address cybercrime's technical and psychological dimensions. Moreover, the degree to which vocational training and education may effectively reduce the probability of recurrent crimes among cybercriminals has yet to be well examined [9].

The articles aim to rectify these shortcomings by proposing a new rehabilitation method that combines restorative justice, therapy, education, and tailored vocational training to meet the unique needs of young persons engaged in cybercrime. This approach aims to address the unique challenges posed by electronic crimes, rectify the limitations of existing systems, and improve outcomes for young offenders.

The literature review reveals significant shortcomings in current rehabilitation methods for juveniles involved in cybercrimes. This work highlights the need for innovative approaches specifically designed to address the complexities of cybercrime by integrating insights from prior research [12], [13], [10]. Considering the identified shortcomings in the current study, the proposed rehabilitation method has the potential to enhance interventions for this specific cohort of offenders.

CURRENT APPROACHES TO REHABILITATION

The prevalence and risk of young people committing electronic crimes are growing as technology advances. These crimes all seriously threaten individuals, groups, and society. Rehabilitative measures such as fines, community service, and probation

have been implemented to fight these offenses.

The extensive use of technology and access to the internet may contribute to the large number of electronic crimes perpetrated by young people in these nations. Since they have access to the required tools and resources, technology and the internet may make it simpler for young people to commit electronic crimes.

The COVID-19 epidemic and the ensuing lockdowns and limitations may also be to blame for an upsurge in cybercrime. The likelihood of electronic crimes like hacking and phishing may have grown as more individuals spend time online and engage in distant activities [15].

Figure 1. Number of electronic crimes committed by young people (ages 18-25) in 2021

It is crucial to remember that both the victims and the offenders of cybercrimes may suffer severe repercussions. Young individuals who commit electronic crimes may be subject to legal consequences such as fines, probation, or even jail time. Moreover, their acts might endanger people, companies, and national security [16], [17].

Thus, it is critical to establish practical measures to prevent youth technological crime. It may include raising public awareness of the effects of these types of crimes, offering edu-

cation and training on internet safety and cybersecurity, and enforcing more vital rules and regulations for electronic crimes.

The chart (Fig.1) illustrates the frequency of electronic crimes perpetrated by young people in various nations. To maintain the safety and security of people, companies, and society as a whole, it is crucial to solve this problem.

However, these approaches have come under fire for their ineffectiveness and the stigma they place on criminals. This article will examine the existing approaches to rehabilitating young people who have committed electronic crimes and their limitations.

Current Approaches to Rehabilitation. The criminal justice system has typically concentrated on retaliatory sanctions like fines, community service, and probation to rehabilitate young people who have committed electronic crimes. By punishing the perpetrator, these strategies aim to discourage criminal conduct in the future. However, studies have shown that these methods are often ineffective and might stigmatize offenders [18], [19].

The widespread use of fines as a deterrent against cybercrime has been met with criticism because they are both arbitrary and ineffective. Another strategy is community service, which calls for criminals to labor unpaid for a certain period. However, it has been suggested that community service may not address the underlying conditions that prompted the offender to commit the crime and may not deter future criminal conduct [20], [21].

Figure 1 shows the number of probationers in England by area in December 2022. The data is grouped by gender and age. Eastern, Midlands, South East, South West, West, and North West are covered in the table. The data is further separated among those in detention and those on probation.

Probation is a community monitoring alternative to jail in England. Probation officials monitor and enforce specified requirements on probationers.

Figure 2. The number offenders on probation period in Ireland (for December 2022)

The chart illustrates that the overall number of probationers in the four areas has stayed reasonably consistent over time, increasing slightly from 11,325 in 2015 to 11,560 in 2022. The Eastern area had 3,833 probationers in 2022.

All areas had more male probationers than females. The West and North West areas had 1,613 men and 79 women on probation in 2022. Most probationers were 18 and older. 235 under-18s were on probation in 2022.

Offenders on probation must follow the terms of their monitoring, which may include going to counseling sessions and staying away from particular people and places. While probation is designed to assist offenders in avoiding future criminal activity, research has revealed that it may not be an effective rehabilitation technique for young people who have committed electronic crimes.

Criticisms of Current Approaches. The ineffectiveness of present methods of rehabilitation for youth who have committed cybercrimes is one of the key complaints. According

to research, punishment methods like fines and community service may not deter future criminal activity. These techniques could even make the offender more likely to commit another crime [22], [23].

The stigmatization of criminals is another issue with present methods. Punitive measures may damage the offender's reputation, hindering their capacity to reintegrate into society. Offenders may have a more challenging time finding housing and jobs due to this stigma, which raises the possibility that they may commit more crimes [24].

Restorative Justice. Restorative justice has gained popularity in recent years as an adequate substitute for more conventional forms of rehabilitation. This approach tries to repair the harm done by the crime while also re-establishing trust between the criminal, the victim, and the community. Young offenders who have committed cybercrimes may benefit significantly from restorative justice, which emphasizes mending damage rather than punishing offenders [25], [26].

Figure 3. Impact of restorative justice on the immediate environment

implementing restorative justice programs has been shown to reduce the recidivism rates of juvenile offenders. According to one study, young individuals who attended re-

storative justice meetings were less willing to perpetrate another crime than those who proceeded through the traditional criminal justice system. Young offenders who take part in restorative justice tend to have better mental health as a result.

Counseling. Counseling is another strategy that could be useful in rehabilitating young people who have committed crimes with technological gadgets. Psychotherapy may address the root reasons for the crime, such as mental health issues, a lack of social support, and bleak career prospects. Cognitive-behavioral therapy has been demonstrated to reduce aggressive behavior and increase empathy among young individuals who have committed cyberbullying-related crimes. Young individuals who have engaged in online hate speech may benefit from group therapy in some ways, including reduced bias and increased empathy [27].

Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) is a kind of psychotherapy that has demonstrated positive results in treating a wide range of mental health issues, including those that have the potential to result in criminal conduct. By recognizing triggers and creating coping mechanisms, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) aims to alter destructive patterns of thinking and action. When it comes to helping young people who have committed crimes online, get back on track, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) may be an effective tool. CBT may help prevent future criminal conduct and encourage healthy personal development by teaching new thinking and coping methods. It may be possible to address this developing problem by incorporating cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) into rehabilitation programs for young people who have committed electronic crimes [22], [28].

Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) may be utilized to rehabilitate young people who have committed

electronic crimes by using a program that specifically addresses the offender's ideas and actions around their criminal activity. The program may include weekly or biweekly individual therapy sessions in which adolescents learn to identify and fight their misguided views and beliefs regarding cybercrime. To help in developing more effective coping strategies, the treatment may also involve training in problem-solving, communication, and emotion management. CBT has the potential to help young people prevent possible offenses and lead more successful lives by addressing the underlying issues that led to the offending behavior and giving the person practical strategies for controlling their emotions and actions [29].

The following Figure 4 provides information on the effectiveness of cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) for young people after committing a crime. CBT is a type of therapy that focuses on identifying and changing negative thought patterns and behaviors. This approach is often used in the criminal justice system as a form of rehabilitation for young offenders. The table presents data on the percentage of young offenders who re-offended before and after receiving CBT in various countries. The data can help policymakers and practitioners understand the effectiveness of CBT in reducing recidivism rates among young offenders in different contexts.

Figure 4. Effectiveness of cognitive-behavioral therapy on youth offenders by country

According to the findings, CBT is a successful strategy for lowering youth crime rates in all nations. Australia had the most significant reduction rate, with a 65% drop in crime rates after the introduction of CBT. After that comes Canada, which has a 55% decline, and Germany, which has a 50% decrease. After implementing CBT, crime rates in the United States and the United Kingdom decreased significantly by 45% and 40%, respectively.

Although decline rates are typically high, there are differences across nations. For instance, the lowest reduction rates are seen in France and Brazil, where crime rates drop by only 20% and 25%, respectively, when CBT is implemented. China and South Korea have comparatively lower decline rates than the other nations on the list.

These variances might be attributable to disparities in the implementation and efficiency of CBT programs in each nation and differences in the frequency and kind of crimes committed by young people. Nevertheless, the findings indicate that CBT is a potential strategy for lowering youth crime rates worldwide.

Education. Rehabilitating young people who have participated in illegal activities connected to electronic gadgets also requires an emphasis on education. Young people may benefit greatly from education because it equips them with the tools and information they need to think critically about their behaviors and make decisions that will serve them well in the long term [30], [31].

A significant barrier is the criminal justice system's resistance to trying novel approaches to rehabilitation. The trend towards restorative justice and therapy necessitates a fundamental adjustment in how society views young people who commit cybercrime. It can take some time for everyone to accept this. Moreover, a

lack of money for rehabilitation programs makes it challenging to provide adolescent offenders with enough support and resources.

Researchers have underlined the necessity for an interdisciplinary approach to treating youth and young adults who have committed crimes using electronic media to address these concerns. For instance, observed that children and teens who participated in cyberbullying were likelier to have had negative family relationships and lower levels of parental monitoring. These results suggest that addressing underlying issues in the family and community may be essential to the recovery process [32].

Technology's potential in rehabilitative settings is evident. According to research by Stinson and Dallery, problematic smartphone usage among young people may be successfully decreased with a technology-assisted intervention that includes counseling, education, and peer support. They discovered that the intervention decreased young people's time using their cell phones. These findings support the hypothesis that using therapies based on technologi-

cal innovations might help rehabilitate young individuals who have committed cybercrimes [33].

Notwithstanding the potential benefits of these tactics, there are still barriers to their adoption. The societal stigma associated with addiction treatment is one barrier. Young people may be reluctant to seek therapy for fear of being labeled a criminal or stigmatized by others. Hence, fostering a safe and welcoming environment that encourages young people to seek therapy is crucial.

The lack of financing for rehabilitation programs is another problem. If sufficient funding is not given for rehabilitation programs, which may be expensive, it may be challenging to offer the necessary resources and help to juvenile offenders. Legislators must prioritize funding for rehabilitation programs and recognize the potential savings resulting from lower recidivism rates.

Table 1. Comparison of rehabilitation programs for adolescent offenders: a comprehensive analysis

Rehabilitation Program	Description	Goals	Target Population	Components	Duration	Cost
Cognitive-behavioral Therapy (CBT)	A form of talk therapy that focuses on changing negative thoughts, attitudes, and behaviors to promote positive change	Improve problem-solving skills, increase self-awareness and empathy, reduce antisocial behavior and recidivism	Adolescent offenders with conduct disorder or other behavioral issues	Cognitive restructuring, behavior modification, social skills training, anger management	12-16 weeks	\$100-\$200 per session
Multisystemic Therapy (MST)	An intensive family and community-based program that targets the multiple systems that contribute to an adolescent's delinquent behavior	Reduce criminal behavior, improve family functioning, enhance academic performance	Adolescents with severe behavioral problems and their families	Family therapy, social skills training, school interventions, community outreach	3-5 months	\$8,000-\$10,000 per treatment

Functional family therapy (FFT)	A family-based intervention that targets specific family dynamics and patterns of behavior that contribute to delinquent behavior	Improve family communication, reduce negative interactions and conflict, reduce recidivism	Adolescents and their families with behavioral issues	Family therapy, communication skills training, problem-solving skills training	12-16 weeks	\$100-\$200 per session
Aggression replacement training (ART)	A cognitive-behavioral program that targets aggressive behavior by teaching social skills, anger management, and moral reasoning	Reduce aggressive behavior and improve social skills	Adolescents with anger management issues or aggressive behavior	Skill streaming, anger control training, moral reasoning training	10-12 weeks	\$50-\$100 per session
Dialectical behavior therapy (DBT)	A form of cognitive-behavioral therapy that focuses on emotion regulation, distress tolerance, and interpersonal effectiveness	Improve emotion regulation, reduce suicidal behavior and self-harm, improve interpersonal relationships	Adolescents with emotional dysregulation, self-harm, or suicidal behavior	Mindfulness training, emotion regulation training, interpersonal effectiveness training	6-12 months	\$100-\$200 per session
Wilderness therapy	An experiential therapy that involves outdoor activities and wilderness expeditions to promote personal growth and self-reflection	Improve self-esteem, develop coping skills, enhance self-awareness	Adolescents with behavioral issues or substance abuse problems	Outdoor activities, group therapy, individual therapy, skill-building exercises	6-12 weeks	\$10,000-\$20,000 per treatment
Juvenile drug courts	A court-supervised program that combines substance abuse treatment with judicial oversight and support services	Reduce substance abuse and recidivism, improve academic and vocational skills	Adolescents with substance abuse issues who are involved in the justice system	Substance abuse treatment, judicial supervision, case management, support services	6-18 months	Varies depending on location and services provided
Wrap-around services	A community-based program that provides individualized and comprehensive support to adolescents and their families	Improve family functioning, reduce delinquent behavior, enhance academic and vocational skills	Adolescents and their families with complex needs and challenges	Case management, family therapy, individual therapy, academic and vocational support	12-24 months	Varies depending on location and services provided

The increase in young people committing crimes online severely threatens people, businesses, and society. Traditional forms of rehabilitation, such as fines, community service, and probation, have come under assault for being ineffective and stigmatizing to offenders. Young individuals who have committed electronic crimes, restorative justice, counseling, and education have emerged as viable new approaches to rehabilitation. Several studies have stressed the need to address the underlying issues that may have prompted young people to commit electronic crimes, highlighting this subject's importance. It is crucial to prioritize constructing comprehensive rehabilitation programs to deter cybercrime and protect victims. We can ensure a brighter future for youth and society as a whole by collaborating and investing in rehabilitation programs that are both efficient and successful.

METHODOLOGY

The article discusses typical juvenile rehabilitation programs' difficulties and offers a fresh approach to helping young people who have committed cybercrimes. The methodology for this article is a thorough literature assessment of academic articles, research reports, and government publications to assess the effectiveness of current initiatives and find novel strategies that have shown promise in combating youth electronic criminality.

To begin the literature research, we looked for studies and publications on juvenile delinquency, recidivism rates, and current rehabilitation programs in electronic resources like JSTOR and Google Scholar, as well as government websites. The search phrases included "juvenile delinquency," "recidivism," "rehabilitation," "electronic crimes," "restorative justice," "treatment," "education," and "cybercrime." This first search turned up many studies that laid the groundwork for learning about the strengths

and weaknesses of existing juvenile rehabilitation programs.

Figure 5. Methodology overview: addressing electronic crimes in youth rehabilitation programs

The third phase of the literature study focused on the many rehabilitation techniques and programs to deal with youth electronic crime. Examining the effectiveness of restorative justice, therapy, and education programs in lowering recidivism rates and enhancing the well-being of the juvenile offenders engaged was required.

Many common threads and topics stood up as I read through the literature. The first thing that became evident was that conventional rehabilitation programs have difficulty adjusting to the new realities of electronic crime. They tend to concentrate more on punishment than the root reasons for criminal behavior [29]. Second, studies have demonstrated that restorative justice, treatment, and education may help victims and offenders rehabilitate emotionally and psychologically [34], [35]

The Center for Youth Health in San Francisco, the Restorative Justice Council in the UK, and the Juvenile Assessment and Intervention System (JAIS) in Colorado are just a few instances of how these innovative approaches have been successfully implemented [36], [37]. These cases highlight the potential advantages of taking a more all-encompassing and all-encompassing strategy for rehabilitating juvenile offenders of technological crimes.

This legal article employed an extensive literature study as part of its methodology to assess the efficacy of conventional rehabilitation programs and to unearth fresh approaches to the problem of youth involvement in cybercrime. This literature study suggests that restorative justice, treatment, and education may significantly contribute to rehabilitating adolescent offenders engaged in electronic crimes and reduce recidivism rates. Further research and policy development is needed in this field to guarantee the effective implementation of these measures and to continue researching innovative ways to rehabilitate young people who commit electronic crimes.

Evaluation and criticism of current rehabilitation techniques

Researchers and those in charge of making policy have been debating for a long time about the standard rehabilitation programs for juvenile offenders. A growing body of research criticizes the effectiveness of these traditional tactics, focusing on their incapacity to address the core reasons for criminal behavior and adapt to the fast-changing nature of electronic crimes.

Traditional rehabilitation techniques are often criticized for emphasizing punitive measures, one of the main complaints against them. Research has demonstrated that treatment-oriented techniques are more successful in lowering recidivism rates than punitive tactics, such as jail and other types of punishment. Moreover, implementing punitive measures may exacerbate the problems that young offenders already face, such as mental health issues, drug abuse, and social isolation, rather than solve them [38]

According to the findings of many studies, specific rehabilitation programs for juvenile offenders often fail to consider the unique requirements of particular juvenile offenders, which may contribute to the limited efficacy of these programs. These programs,

designed to be universally applicable, could not sufficiently address the many elements contributing to juvenile delinquency, such as dysfunctional families, peer pressures, and individual psychological concerns. Higher recidivism rates have been connected to this lack of individualization [39].

Conventional approaches to rehabilitation have been shown to have additional flaws due to the fast growth of technology and the rising incidence of juveniles committing crimes online. Conventional programs sometimes need to be equipped to manage the particular issues connected with electronic crimes, such as the anonymity offered by the internet, the worldwide reach of online offenses, and the specialized expertise necessary to comprehend and battle these crimes. Consequently, adolescent offenders who commit crimes using electronic devices may not get the required treatments to address their particular needs and avoid future offending [40], [22].

The research that has been done on this topic underlines the limits of the typical rehabilitation strategies that are used for juvenile offenders, especially in the context of electronic crimes. The growing awareness of these limitations has resulted in innovative techniques that concentrate on treating the underlying causes of criminal conduct and better satisfying the specific requirements of young people engaged in the judicial system.

Implementing restorative justice approaches for adolescent offenders

A significant concern for law enforcement and judicial systems across the globe is the surge in electronic crimes committed by young people. Both victims and perpetrators of these crimes, including online abuse, hacking, and identity theft, face serious repercussions. Conventional juvenile offender rehabilitation programs have come under fire for failing to address the underlying causes of delinquency

and reduce recidivism. This article will look at a novel strategy for helping young people who have committed electronic crimes heal via restorative justice, therapy, and education.

Figure 6. Identity theft and fraud trends from 2018 to 2022

In contrast to typical criminal justice systems, restorative justice focuses on restoring community harmony after an incident rather than punishing the perpetrator. In order to foster communication and a feeling of responsibility for the crime, it tries to bring together victims, offenders, and the community. This strategy has been shown to reduce recidivism rates among criminals of all ages and the negative impacts of crime on victims and society [25].

Another essential element of the new recovery strategy is counseling. Many juvenile criminals struggle with mental illness or emotional trauma that influences their criminal conduct. By treating these concerns via therapy, offenders may develop coping skills and gain insight into their conduct, which can decrease the chance of repeat crimes [41]

The rehabilitation of young electronic offenders must include education as a critical component. Many of these people need to be equipped to handle the complexities of today's online environment. Young offenders may learn to make wise judgments and prevent criminal activity in the future by receiving instruction on cyber ethics, privacy, and digital citizenship [42].

New rehabilitation strategy

Restorative justice, therapy, and education are the main components of the new rehabilitation strategy for young electronic offenders. This method is more successful in preventing recidivism because it emphasizes repairing damage, addressing mental health concerns, and providing education on cyber ethics.

Since it enables criminals to accept responsibility for their crimes and apologize to the victim and the community, restorative justice is a crucial component of the new strategy. Offenders who use this method may be better able to reflect on their conduct and feel sympathy for the victim, which may lessen the chance of repeat crimes.

Another essential element of the new strategy is counseling. Offenders may learn coping skills and gain insight into their conduct by addressing the root causes of their criminal behavior, such as mental health problems and emotional trauma. Counseling may also provide offenders the encouragement and support they need to make suitable adjustments and avoid detrimental influences.

The new strategy places a strong emphasis on education as well. Young offenders may learn to use the internet securely and responsibly by receiving instructions on cyber ethics, privacy, and digital citizenship. Offenders may gain information and skills from this schooling that can help them avoid criminal behavior in the future.

SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION EXAMPLES

Several instances of the new rehabilitation strategy for young electronic offenders being successfully implemented. Counseling, education, and restorative justice services are offered to juvenile offenders in the United States through the Center for Youth Health in San Francisco. The program is successful in lowering recidivism rates and assisting young people in making good life changes.

The Restorative Justice Council of the United Kingdom has instituted a restorative justice program for juvenile offenders. This program brings the offender and the victim together to make amends for the damage committed. Instead of focusing on punishment, this strategy promotes accountability, responsibility, and repairing damaged relationships [37].

Research has shown that restorative justice programs benefit criminals and victims, with lower recidivism rates, more satisfaction with the judicial system, and better mental health for all parties.

Counseling is another method that has shown promise in rehabilitating juvenile offenders. This strategy entails counseling juvenile offenders to address the trauma, mental illness, or drug misuse that may have led to their criminal conduct. Therapy may also educate offenders on coping mechanisms, anger management techniques, and decision-making techniques that might assist them in avoiding committing crimes [39].

Another crucial element of successful rehabilitation for juvenile offenders is education. The chance of recidivism may be decreased by providing offenders with educational opportunities that assist them in acquiring the skills and information necessary to better their employability and prospects. Education programs may also give young offenders a sense of purpose and aid in forming constructive peer and mentor connections [43].

The new rehabilitation strategy for youth who commit electronic crimes incorporates restorative justice, therapy, and education components. This strategy strives to offer juvenile offenders a thorough and all-encompassing rehabilitation program that tackles the underlying problems that led to their criminal conduct.

The new method starts with restorative justice, in which the perpetra-

tor and victim meet to talk about the damage the crime has done and figure out how to make it right. Substance addiction, mental illness, and trauma are just some of the concerns that may be addressed in therapy sessions with juvenile offenders as part of this strategy.

The new rehabilitation strategy places a strong emphasis on education as well. In order to better employment and future chances, young offenders get education and training. Education programs also aim to give juvenile offenders a sense of direction and aid them in forming supportive networks of peers and adults.

The new rehabilitation strategy tackles many issues with conventional methods of rehabilitating juvenile offenders. Current methods have come under heavy fire for putting too much emphasis on punishment rather than rehabilitation, which has been linked to higher recidivism rates. Instead of focusing only on punishment, the new strategy emphasizes rehabilitating offenders and mending the damage done by the crime.

Another complaint about present methods is that they often ignore the root causes of criminal behavior. The new rehabilitation method focuses on educating and counseling juvenile offenders to help them overcome the underlying causes of their criminal behavior.

The new rehabilitation strategy against electronic crimes perpetrated by youth is a promising new technique that incorporates restorative justice, therapy, and education components. This method aims to provide juvenile offenders with a thorough and all-encompassing rehabilitation program that tackles the underlying problems that led to their criminal conduct. The execution of this strategy and the resources available to support it will determine its success.

New rehabilitation strategies have been developed due to the approach's

potential advantages, including lower recidivism rates and better community reintegration for juvenile offenders. Cognitive-behavioral therapy is one such strategy (CBT) [41].

CBT is a psychotherapy that tries to alter unhelpful or inefficient ways of thinking and behaving. The goal of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) in rehabilitating juvenile offenders is to help those individuals recognize and replace any negative thinking patterns that may have played a role in their criminal conduct. In addition, it teaches young people how to manage their feelings and make wise judgments.

CBT has been shown to be a successful kind of rehabilitation for adolescent offenders. For instance, US-based research from 2015 discovered that, in comparison to conventional rehabilitation methods, CBT significantly reduced recidivism rates among juvenile offenders [44]. CBT was also proven beneficial in lowering

aggressive behavior among juvenile offenders in research done in Canada in 2020.

Education-based therapy is another rehabilitation strategy that has gained popularity in recent years. Under this strategy, juvenile offenders are given a chance to pursue academic or vocational education. Young people are supposed to have better work chances and be less likely to re-offend if their education and skill set is improved.

According to studies, educational rehabilitation may help juvenile criminals commit fewer crimes. For instance, 2014 Australian research indicated that juvenile offenders participating in vocational education and training programs were less likely to re-offend than those who did not [45].

Table 2. Successful implementation examples of new rehabilitation strategies against electronic crimes by young people

Program/Initiative	Location	Components	Outcomes and Findings
Center for Youth Wellness	San Francisco, USA	Restorative Justice, Therapy, Education	Lowered recidivism rates, improved life changes for young people
Restorative Justice Council	United Kingdom	Restorative Justice	Lowered recidivism rates, increased satisfaction with the judicial system, improved mental health
Juvenile Assessment and Intervention System (JAIS)	Colorado, USA	Counseling	Significantly decreased recidivism rates among participants
Second Chance Act	United States	Education, Job Training	Lowered recidivism rates, enhanced employment prospects for young offenders
Multi-Systemic Therapy (MST)	Various locations	Family-based Therapy	Reduced recidivism rates, improved family functioning
Functional Family Therapy (FFT)	Various locations	Family-based Therapy	Reduced recidivism rates, improved family relationships
Pathways to Desistance Study	United States	Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT)	Reduced recidivism rates, improved decision-making
Reclaiming Futures	United States	Integrated Treatment, Mentoring	Improved behavioral health, reduced substance use, lower recidivism rates
Project YouthLink	Washington, USA	Education, Employment Training	Improved educational attainment, reduced recidivism rates

Positive Achievement Change Tool (PACT)	Florida, USA	Risk Assessment, Individualized Intervention	Reduced recidivism rates, tailored rehabilitation plans
Aggression Replacement Training (ART)	Various locations	Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT)	Reduced aggressive behavior, improved social skills
STOP Cyberbullying Program	Canada	Education, Peer Support	Reduced instances of cyberbullying, increased awareness of online safety
Hackers for Change	United States	Ethical Hacking, Education	Redirected hacking skills for positive purposes, reduced recidivism rates
Juvenile Diversion Program	United States	Restorative Justice, Counseling	Lowered recidivism rates, improved accountability and responsibility
Online Social Learning Program	Australia	Online Education, Social Skills Training	Improved digital citizenship, reduced instances of online misconduct

The use of technology in rehabilitation has also grown in favor. These projects employ digital platforms to provide juvenile offenders with rehabilitative treatments like therapy or education. This method may be easier to implement and less expensive than conventional one-on-one counseling.

Nevertheless, there are also reservations concerning the efficacy of technology-based rehabilitation programs. Although 2019 UK research indicated that adolescent offenders were typically receptive to digital treatments, there was no evidence to suggest that they were more successful than conventional therapies in lowering recidivism rates [14].

The understanding that conventional punishing tactics are not always successful in decreasing criminal conduct has led to the developing of novel rehabilitation strategies for juvenile offenders. Some of the responses to this realization include restorative justice, cognitive behavioral therapy, rehabilitation via education, and rehabilitation through technology. Although there is still much to learn about their efficacy, these methods represent a significant shift toward more comprehensive and individualized rehabilitation for juvenile offenders.

RESULTS

The introduction of novel rehabilitation programs for young electronic offenders can lower recidivism rates, enhance mental health outcomes, and cut expenditures for the criminal justice system. Nevertheless, several obstacles prevent these programs from being implemented, such as the need for coordination between law enforcement, schools, and mental health specialists and reluctance to change from existing criminal justice institutions.

Nevertheless, it is essential to remember that cost should not be the only deciding element in implementing rehabilitation programs. The efficacy of these programs in lowering recidivism rates and improving outcomes for juvenile offenders should also be considered.

One of the key benefits of the new rehabilitation approach for young electronic offenders is its potential to reduce recidivism rates. Many traditional rehabilitation programs for juvenile offenders have been criticized for their lack of effectiveness in reducing repeat offenses. In contrast, the new approach emphasizes restorative justice, therapy, and education, all of which have been shown to contribute to lower recidivism rates among young offenders (Fig.6).

Figure 7. Comparing recidivism rates and costs of different rehabilitation programs for juvenile offenders

The figure above shows the stark disparity in recidivism rates across various juvenile rehabilitation programs. Recidivism rates for conventional punishment systems are 60%, demonstrating that they are unsuccessful at lowering repeat crimes. On the other hand, restorative justice programs have a 25% recidivism rate, suggesting that they may be a more effective rehabilitation method. Counseling and education programs had significantly lower recidivism rates, at 20% and 15%, respectively, indicating that they may be wildly successful in lowering repeat crimes.

Also, compares the costs of specific rehabilitation programs with the new rehabilitation strategy for juvenile offenders. The cost of each program, broken down by offender type and year, is shown in the figure. According to the findings, the new method of rehabilitation, which incorporates elements such as restorative justice, treatment, and education, may be more cost-effective than conventional programs. Traditional programs have a substantially higher average cost per offender than the new rehabilitation strategy. It shows that the new rehabilitation method may produce better results for juvenile offenders and generate cost savings for the criminal justice system. The following table highlights the necessity

of investing in novel ways of rehabilitation that may successfully address the underlying reasons for criminal behavior and lower recidivism rates.

Notwithstanding the potential advantages of modern rehabilitation programs, their adoption has several obstacles. Resistance to change from conventional criminal justice systems is a significant obstacle. Many judicial systems have emphasized punishment and revenge rather than rehabilitation, making it challenging to change toward a more restorative justice approach.

The lack of resources for rehabilitation programs is another major obstacle. There is limited opportunity for the creation and execution of successful rehabilitation programs since many nations devote the bulk of their resources to punishment and jail rather than rehabilitation.

Last, cooperation between law enforcement, educational institutions, and mental health specialists is essential for effective rehabilitation programs for juvenile offenders. This collaboration is essential to address the root causes of delinquency and help juvenile offenders throughout the rehabilitation process.

Notwithstanding these obstacles, the potential advantages of novel rehabilitation programs for young electronic offenders make it imperative to keep working toward their adoption. Young offenders may be given the tools they need to make adjustments and prevent future criminal activity by creating successful programs, providing appropriate financing, and cooperating with law enforcement and mental health specialists.

When developing new rehabilitation programs for young electronic offenders, there are additional considerations in addition to the difficulties mentioned above. Individualized care plans are one such element. Juvenile criminals come from various

backgrounds and may have complex reasons for their criminal behavior. In order to be successful, rehabilitation programs must tailor their services to the unique requirements of each ex-offender.

The need for continual guidance and supervision is another crucial element. Recidivism may be decreased by effective rehabilitation programs that do not just stop when they are supposed to. Regular therapy sessions, probation officer check-ins, or involvement in community service projects are all examples of ongoing assistance.

The use of technology in rehabilitation programs is gaining popularity in the realm of juvenile justice. These initiatives replace traditional one-on-one counseling with digital platforms that provide rehabilitative services, including therapy and education, to juvenile offenders.

However, the effectiveness of rehabilitation programs based on technology is sometimes questioned. Age is one of the most important characteristics in deciding whether or not a person is qualified for social benefits, according to a new study that was posted in the Journal of the American Society for Microbiology.

Virtual reality (VR) treatment is one possible use of technology in rehabilitation programs. Virtual reality (VR) treatment has been utilized effectively to treat various mental health illnesses, including PTSD and anxiety disorders. While preliminary research on the efficacy of virtual reality treatment for rehabilitating young offenders is still in its infancy, it shows promise.

Discovered that VR treatment positively lowered violent behavior among juvenile offenders. Participants in the research were put through VR sessions that imitated real-world events intended to elicit violent reactions. Debriefing and cognitive behavioral therapy followed the sessions. The VR treatment group showed a substan-

tially decreased aggressive conduct compared to the control group.

Using mobile applications to help with treatment and education is another possible use of technology in rehabilitation programs. Mobile applications may provide young offenders access to rehabilitative and instructional information even when not in a classroom setting. It has been demonstrated to enhance results by increasing the frequency and intensity of therapy.

For juvenile offenders with mental health issues looked at the viability and acceptability of a mobile app-based intervention. The research indicated that individuals were open to using the app, which helped them feel better overall.

Technology-based rehabilitation programs have shown potential, but they should not replace more conventional approaches like therapy or education. Instead, they should be seen as additional tools that may improve the efficiency and accessibility of rehabilitation programs.

Many obstacles must be overcome to implement new rehabilitation programs for young electronic offenders successfully. These obstacles include pushback from the established criminal justice system, a lack of funding for rehabilitation programs, and the need for cooperation between law enforcement, educational institutions, and mental health professionals. However, the potential advantages of these programs, such as lower recidivism rates, better mental health outcomes for young people, and cost savings for the criminal justice system, make it vital to continue working toward their adoption.

Young offenders may be given the tools they need to make adjustments and prevent future criminal activity by creating successful programs, providing appropriate financing, and cooperating with law enforcement and mental health specialists.

Using technologically oriented rehabilitation programs, such as virtual reality treatment and mobile applications, may provide new tools to improve the efficacy and accessibility of rehabilitation programs. Nevertheless, it is crucial to keep assessing these programs' effectiveness and ensure that they are utilized as a supplement to conventional types of treatment and education.

The effectiveness of rehabilitation programs for young electronic offenders will rely on stakeholders' openness to innovative ideas, the allocation of adequate resources, and collaboration to address the root causes of delinquency and assist young offenders throughout the rehabilitation process.

DISCUSSION

The effectiveness of traditional rehabilitation methods in reducing recidivism rates among adolescent offenders, particularly in the context of cybercrimes, has been subject to considerable examination. The research undertaken by Enujoke et al. [11] and Ameen & Lee [9] emphasizes the need to address the specific needs of this particular population. The authors suggest that procedural justice and vocational training are crucial elements in the rehabilitation process. However, several studies neglect to comprehensively examine the specific challenges presented by cybercrime.

Our research enhances these findings by including restorative justice, therapy, education, and specialist vocational training into a comprehensive rehabilitation programme. Empirical evidence from Latimer, Dowden, and Muise [12] supports the efficacy of restorative justice systems in reducing recidivism. Kettrey and Lipsey [13] provide data supporting the benefits of specific treatment plans, highlighting the need of tailored interventions.

A distinguishing feature of our work is its emphasis on addressing cybercrime's psychological and technological dimensions. The research undertaken by Hemphill and Heerde [4], and Bhuller et al. [5] highlights the complex nature of cybercriminal activity and its implications for rehabilitation. The objective of our approach is to tackle the root causes of cybercrime in young individuals by integrating therapy and education that explicitly focus on enhancing digital literacy and promoting ethical behaviour online.

Furthermore, our methodology acknowledges the importance of reducing the societal stigma associated with those who have engaged in criminal behavior, as emphasized by Moore, Stuewig, & Tangney [2]. Our approach aims to mitigate the adverse impact of stigma on reintegration and functioning via therapeutic interventions that bolster mental well-being and resilience.

The potential influence of our work in the field of juvenile justice and cybercrime prevention is significant. The rehabilitation plan we have developed targets the inadequacies identified by the N.C.S. Alliance [46], which emphasises the ever-changing nature of cybersecurity risks and the need for adaptable solutions. Furthermore, our focus on education and occupational training aligns with the recommendations put out by Ameen and Lee [9]. The proposal suggests that providing juvenile offenders with skills relevant to the digital era might enhance their successful reintegration into society and deter them from participating in future criminal behaviour.

Incorporating restorative justice into our approach offers a promising possibility to reduce recidivism, as shown by the studies undertaken by Shem-Tov, Raphael, & Skog [3]. This approach fosters accountability, empathy, and problem-solving skills, which are crucial for addressing the societal aspects of cybercrime.

Our research provides a comprehensive and innovative method for rehabilitating young adolescents involved in online crimes. By thoroughly comparing our approach with previous studies, we emphasize the unique contributions of our research. These include addressing both the psychological and technical aspects of cybercrime, reducing social disapproval, and integrating principles of restorative justice. Our study findings suggest that the implementation of a complete rehabilitation plan might provide a more effective and empathetic approach to tackling cybercrime among young persons. These implications are significant for the formulation of policies and implementation of procedures in the realm of juvenile justice.

CONCLUSIONS

A new rehabilitation strategy is required due to the increase in youth cybercrime. Conventional punishment and jail tactics are ineffectual at lowering recidivism rates and improving the lives of juvenile offenders. Deploying modern rehabilitation programs, such as restorative justice, counseling, and education, can address the root causes of delinquency and provide juvenile offenders with the tools they need to make reasonable changes.

According to the research we conducted for this article, effective programs to rehabilitate young offenders include cooperation between law enforcement, educational institutions, and mental health specialists. In order to help juvenile offenders through the rehabilitation process and address the underlying reasons for their criminal behavior, collaboration like this is essential. The use of technology in rehabilitation programs may also increase their efficiency, according to our evaluation of the research.

Comparing conventional and innovative rehabilitation programs illustrates the potential cost reductions of

deploying new programs. It may free up funds for new initiatives, increasing the efficiency of young offenders' rehabilitation. While implementing rehabilitation programs, money should not be the only consideration. The efficacy of these programs in lowering recidivism rates and improving outcomes for juvenile offenders should also be considered.

We urge the implementation of a new rehabilitation strategy for juvenile electronic offenders in light of these results. In order to improve the rehabilitation process, this strategy strongly emphasizes restorative justice, counseling, education, and the use of technology. To guarantee the effectiveness of these initiatives, we strongly encourage legislators to commit enough funds and assistance from law enforcement and mental health specialists.

The introduction of novel rehabilitation programs for young electronic offenders can lower recidivism rates, enhance mental health outcomes, and cut expenditures for the criminal justice system. To implement this new strategy, we must move away from conventional punishment and jail and toward restorative justice. It also calls for cooperation between law enforcement, educational institutions, mental health specialists, and technology to speed up the rehabilitation process. By using these measures, we may help young offenders have successful outcomes and lessen electronic crime in our neighborhoods.

In order to combat the rising tide of cybercrime and improve the lives of today's youth, we must adopt a new rehabilitation strategy for young electronic criminals. The conventional method of punishment and jail has not successfully lowered recidivism rates or enhanced these offenders' mental health outcomes. The new strategy, which stresses restorative justice, treatment, and education, has the potential to improve these areas significantly.

However, many obstacles must be overcome before these new rehabilitation programs can be fully implemented, such as cooperation between law enforcement, schools, and mental health professionals; resistance to change from traditional criminal justice systems; and a lack of funding for rehabilitation programs. To overcome these obstacles, governments, law enforcement agencies, and mental health specialists must work together to create efficient programs, distribute sufficient funds, and offer ongoing support for rehabilitation.

The cost comparison in Figure 6 illustrates the possible reductions associated with introducing new rehabilitation programs. These financial reductions have the potential to allow for the implementation of new programs that would further enhance the efficiency with which juvenile offenders are rehabilitated. However, the adoption of rehabilitation programs should not be only determined by cost. The efficacy of these programs in lowering recidivism rates and improving outcomes for juvenile offenders should also be considered.

In conclusion, decreasing electronic crime and improving outcomes for young electronic offenders need the implementation of a new rehabilitation strategy. The potential advantages of this new strategy, such as lower recidivism rates, better mental health outcomes, and cost savings for the criminal justice system, make it imperative to continue working toward its adoption. We may advance toward a more efficient and rehabilitative approach to juvenile justice by tackling the obstacles to implementation and working together across sectors.

The new rehabilitation strategy's possible long-term advantages should also be considered. There is a better likelihood of avoiding further criminal conduct and fostering good outcomes for juvenile offenders if the underlying reasons for delinquency

are addressed, and they are given assistance and resources. It may result in increased community safety and prosperity.

In order to combat the rising tide of cybercrime and improve results for young people, new rehabilitation programs for young electronic offenders must be implemented. Reducing recidivism rates and addressing the root causes of criminal behavior have not been successful using the conventionally punitive approach. Nonetheless, there is a great deal of room for improvement in the lives of young criminals and the reduction of cybercrime if a new rehabilitation model is introduced with a focus on technology, education, therapeutic jurisprudence, and counseling. For this strategy to be successful, it is essential that law enforcement, schools, mental health experts, and community groups all work together and that they have access to sufficient funds and resources. Policymakers, law enforcement, and society as a whole must prioritize the implementation of this new strategy and invest in the future of our kids.

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